

UTILIZATION OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION CURRICULUM IN FEDERAL AND STATE UNIVERSITIES IN ANAMBRA STATE, NIGERIA

Okoye, Faith Ogechukwu¹ⁱ,

Duru, Daniel Chigozie²

¹PhD, Department of Educational Management and Policy,
Faculty of Education,
Nnamdi Azikiwe University,
Awka, Nigeria

²Department of Educational Management and Policy,
Faculty of Education,
Nnamdi Azikiwe University,
Awka, Nigeria

Abstract:

The study investigated the utilization of entrepreneurship education curriculum in federal and state universities in Anambra State. Three research questions and one hypothesis guided the study. Descriptive survey research design was adopted. 7,850 undergraduate students constituted the population of the study; while stratified random sampling technique was used to draw 240 respondents as the sample from the state and federal universities in Anambra State. A 21 item questionnaire developed by the researchers was used for data collection. The validation of the instrument was done by three experts, two in Educational Management and Policy and an expert in Measurement and Evaluation Unit of Educational Foundations Department of Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. Data obtained were analyzed through mean and t-test statistic. The findings indicated high extent of utilization of NUC benchmark yet specific objectives were unattained. Based on the findings, the study recommended among others that university management should endeavour to adopt appropriate teaching methods in teaching of entrepreneurship education and that the curriculum focus should continue to be practical oriented to enable the achievement of the specified objectives in equipping the undergraduate with relevant skills for self-sustainability on graduation.

Keywords: entrepreneurship education, entrepreneurship curriculum, federal and state universities

ⁱ Correspondence: email danielduru47@gmail.com

1. Introduction

Education is a viable tool for individual and national development. Through education, a nation prepares and functionally integrates her young generation into the society. Though one of the national education goals is the acquisition of appropriate skills and the development of mental, physical, social abilities and competencies as equipment for the individual to live in, and contribute to the development of the society (Federal Republic of Nigeria FRN, 2013). The problem of integrating young graduates into the social and economic systems seems to be unsolved in Nigeria.

Adejimola and Olufunmilayo (2009) stated that the problem with Nigerian education is that too much emphasis is laid on the value of the qualification rather than the holder. In other words, undergraduates are inspired to struggle hard to obtain degree certificates rather than the knowledge and skills that would enable them to be self-reliant. This incessant craving for academic qualification without acquisition of competent skills appears to be a major factor necessitating the high rate of graduate unemployment in the nation.

This high level of graduate unemployment has been a worrisome issue demanding for urgent attention. Yahaya (2006) in his opinion suggested that the best way to solve this problem of graduate unemployment is to ensure that students in institutions of higher learning undertake compulsory entrepreneurship study courses. Adopting this as measure of tackling the challenge of graduate unemployment in Nigeria, the federal government directed all universities, polytechnics and colleges of education to include entrepreneurship education as part of their curricula, starting from the 2007/2008 academic session (Nwekeaku, 2013). For the universities, the mandate was to be implemented through the National Universities Commission, whereas the National Board for Technical Education and National Commission for Colleges of Education were responsible for the polytechnics and colleges of education respectively (Ikebuaku & Dinbabo, 2018).

Entrepreneurship education as a matter of fact has continued to feature as a captivating theme in local summits and international conferences because of its potency as a tool for palliating unemployment and other socio-economic challenges hindering sustainable development (Wordu & Adeeyo, 2019). Entrepreneurship education is the process of acquiring knowledge, special skills and experiences by individuals for effective conquering and adaptation to the environment (Nwekeaku, 2013). According to Aliu (2014), it is learning directed towards developing in young people those skills, competencies, understanding, and attributes which equip them to be innovative, and training them to identify, create, initiate, and successfully manage personal or community businesses, and work opportunities.

Curriculum is defined as the whole spectrum of content, resources, materials and method of teaching by which the objectives of education are accomplished (Wasagu in Ejoja & Odu, 2016). In the light of this, Obi & Okekeokosisi (2018) defined entrepreneurship education curriculum as the step by step designed program that informs, train, educate, monitor and evaluate entrepreneurs in the society. It is the

embodiments of activities, actions and predispositions that instill the passion for creativity. A good entrepreneurship curriculum should be comprehensive, dynamic and responsive to changing needs (Ekoja and Odu, 2016).

According to the NUC (2007), the curriculum of universities on entrepreneurship course for undergraduates is meant to cover the following broad areas: introduction to entrepreneurship and new venture creation; entrepreneurship in theory and practice; the opportunity, forms of business, staffing, marketing and the new venture; determining capital requirements, raising capital; financial planning and management; starting a new business, feasibility studies; innovation; legal issues; insurance and environmental considerations. In addition to these, undergraduate students are expected to be taught one or two practical skills of their interest that will enable them to be self-employed on graduation.

These practical skills includes: soap making, tooth brushes and tooth paste making, photography, brick, nails and screws making, plumbing, vulcanizing, glassware and ceramic production, paper production, water treatment, conditioning and packaging, food processing, packaging and preservation, metal working and fabrication, vegetable oil and salt extractions, fisheries, refrigeration and air conditioning repair, plastic making, crop farming, domestic electrical wiring, radio and television repair, bakery, tailoring, iron welding, carpentry, leather tanning, interior decoration, printing, animal husbandry, metal craft, vehicle maintenance and bookkeeping (NUC, 2007).

Curriculum implementation is said to be the planning and execution of the contents of curriculum in order to bring about certain changes in the behaviour of the learners and the assessment of the extent to which the changes take place (Offorma in Obi & Okekeokosisi, 2018). According to Hadiza and Garba (2015), the goal of entrepreneurship education is to empower graduates irrespective of their areas of specialization with skills that will enable them to engage in income yielding venture, if they are unable to secure jobs in the public sector. The universities entrepreneurship education curriculum seems not to have done much in equipping the undergraduates with entrepreneurial skills for self-employment and self-sustainability after graduation. Greater number of graduates are still searching for employment or being underemployed. A recent publication by National Bureau of Statistics (2018) indicated that 55.4% of young people in the labour force, aged 15-34 years were either underemployed or unemployed. These age groups have a combined unemployment and underemployment rate of 24.5 million (13.1 million unemployed and 11.3 million underemployed).

Edokpolor and Somorin (2017) also observed that entrepreneurship education curriculum is not properly implemented particularly at the university level and that students are not well-equipped with entrepreneurship key competencies such as creative and innovative skills that would have helped them in starting and running their own business. However, the reason behind graduates not being able to engage in entrepreneurial practice after graduation despite having passed through entrepreneurship education studies is yet to be ascertained. Nwite (2016) reported that

entrepreneurial learning environment and support tools were not available in higher institutions in Nigeria and that adequate teachers to provide the needed appropriate skills and right attitude were not available and where they were available, they were in shortfall. Considering the objectives of entrepreneurship education in universities, its curriculum ought to have been focused on practical skills other than just theoretical concepts, adequate number of experts in various skills are supposed to have been employed to facilitate the study.

Prior to this study, there are various cross-sectional surveys conducted by researchers to investigate the integration, implementation and utilization of entrepreneurship education both at the federal and state universities in Anambra state. There was a mismatch between the integration of entrepreneurship education in the universities and reduction in the high rate of university graduate unemployment in the state. Thus, this phenomenon necessitated the need for further investigation of the utilization of entrepreneurship education curriculum in federal and state Universities in Anambra State.

2. Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to assess the utilization of entrepreneurship education curriculum in federal and state universities in Anambra state. Specifically, the study investigated the extent to which:

- 1) federal and state universities in Anambra state utilize NUC benchmark in teaching of entrepreneurship education.
- 2) entrepreneurial practical skills are taught in federal and state universities in Anambra State.
- 3) facilities are made available for teaching of entrepreneurship education in federal and state universities in Anambra State.

2.1 Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- 1) To what extent do federal and state universities in Anambra state utilize NUC benchmark in teaching of entrepreneurship education?
- 2) To what extent are entrepreneurial practical skills taught in federal and state universities in Anambra State?
- 3) To what extent are facilities made available for teaching of entrepreneurship education in federal and state universities in Anambra State?

2.2 Hypothesis

Ho1: There is no significant difference between responses of federal and state university students on the extent of utilization of entrepreneurship education curriculum in tertiary institutions in Anambra State.

3. Method

The design of the study was descriptive survey aimed at investigating the utilization of entrepreneurship education curriculum in federal and state universities in Anambra state. The population of the study comprised 7,850 undergraduates who have passed through entrepreneurship education studies in federal and state universities in Anambra state. A sample of 240 respondents was drawn using stratified random sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was a 21 item structured questionnaire designed by the researchers.

Each of the items was rated on a 4- point scale of Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE), and Very Low Extent (VLE). The instrument was face validated by three research experts, two in Educational Management and Policy and one in Measurement and Evaluation all in Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. The internal consistency of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha method and reliability coefficients for the clusters were as follows; cluster A: 0.75 cluster B: 0.82 and cluster C: 0.85. Data collected were analyzed using mean to answer the research questions, and t-test to test the null hypothesis at 0.5 level of significance. The mean values were interpreted as follows; less than 1.5 (VLE); 1.5-2.49 (LE); 2.50-3.50 (HE); 3.50 and above (VHE), while the hypothesis was accepted if the table value is greater than or equal to the calculated or critical value and rejected if otherwise.

4. Results

Research Question 1: To what extent do federal and state universities in Anambra state utilize NUC benchmark in teaching of entrepreneurship education?

Table 1: Mean response of state and federal university students on the extent to which NUC benchmark is used in teaching of entrepreneurship education in universities in Anambra State?

S/N	Use of NUC Benchmark Items	Federal University N = 120 Mean	State University N = 120 Mean	Total N = 240 Mean	Decision
1	My institution possess the NUC entrepreneurship curriculum guideline	3.13	2.75	2.94	High Extent
2	We have a well-equipped entrepreneurship development centre	2.63	2.63	2.63	High Extent
3	The curriculum guides teaching of entrepreneurship studies	3.13	3.13	3.13	High Extent
4	Specified objectives are attained	2.50	2.25	2.38	Low Extent
5	Recommended teaching strategies are used	2.38	3.13	2.76	High Extent
6	Specified assessment of tools are adopted	2.50	2.50	2.50	High Extent
7	Required instructional materials are used	3.13	3.13	3.13	High

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					Extent
8	Unavailable resource are improvised	2.25	2.25	2.25	Low Extent
Over All Mean		2.71	2.72	2.72	High Extent

Table 1 indicates that the overall mean response of students of both federal and state universities of all the items in the cluster were more than 2.50 except item 4 and 8. The overall mean of the cluster 2.72 indicates high extent. This shows that federal and state universities in Anambra state to a high extent do utilize NUC benchmark in teaching of entrepreneurship education.

Research Question 2: To what extent are entrepreneurial practical skills taught in federal and state universities in Anambra State?

Table 2: Mean response of state and federal university students on the extent to which entrepreneurial practical skills are taught in universities in Anambra State?

Entrepreneurial Practical Skills		Federal University N = 120 Mean	State University N = 120 Mean	Total N = 240 Mean	Decision
S/N	Items				
9	My institution does not have expert facilitators on various entrepreneurial practical skills.	3.13	3.00	3.07	High Extent
10	There are varieties of practical skills options to which a student can choose from in my school.	3.00	3.13	3.07	High Extent
11	Involvement in any practical skill is based on the students' choice and not on school placement.	3.25	3.00	3.13	High Extent
12	Lecturer students' ratio in entrepreneurship practical classes is encouraging.	2.63	3.13	2.88	High Extent
13	The method of teaching used by the facilitators of the practical skills enhances students understanding and mastery of the skills.	3.38	3.13	3.26	High Extent
14	Facilitators are tolerant with the students' behaviours as they learn the various skills.	2.63	2.63	2.63	High Extent
Over All Mean		3.00	3.00	3.00	High Extent

Table 2 indicates that the overall mean response of students of both federal and state universities to items 9-14 were more than 2.50. This shows that entrepreneurial practical skills to a high extent are taught in federal and state universities in Anambra state.

Research Question 3: To what extent are facilities made available for teaching of entrepreneurship education in federal and state universities in Anambra State?

Table 3: Mean response of state and federal university students on the extent to which facilities are made available for teaching of entrepreneurship education in universities in Anambra State?

Availability of Facilities		Federal University N = 120 Mean	State University N = 120 Mean	Total N = 240 Mean	Decision
15	We have well equipped workshops for entrepreneurship practical	3.00	3.00	3.00	High Extent
16	Relevant entrepreneurship texts and journals are in stocked	2.38	3.50	2.94	High Extent
17	Our entrepreneurship workshops are sizeable to accommodate all students offering entrepreneurship course	2.38	2.25	2.32	Low Extent
18	All our workshops have functional machines that are being maintained over time.	2.25	2.88	2.56	High Extent
19	Classrooms for entrepreneurship lectures are large and conducive to accommodate the students.	3.25	3.25	3.25	High Extent
20	Entrepreneurship learning materials are adequately provided by my school	2.75	3.50	3.13	High Extent
21	Hand tools are available for students to practice with during and after training sessions.	3.00	2.25	2.63	High Extent
Over All Mean		2.72	2.95	2.83	High Extent

Table 3 indicates that the overall mean response of students of both federal and state universities to items 9-14 in the cluster were more than 2.50 except item 17. This shows that facilities to a high extent are made available in federal and state universities in Anambra state.

4.1 Test of Hypothesis

Ho1: There is no significant difference between responses of federal and state university students on the extent of utilization of entrepreneurship education curriculum in tertiary institutions in Anambra State.

Table 4: Summary of t-test analysis of significant difference between the mean responses of students of federal and state universities on the extent of utilization of entrepreneurship education curriculum in tertiary institutions in Anambra State

Group	Mean	SD	N	Df	t-cal	Level of Sig.	t-value	Decision
Federal University	2.81	0.94	120	238	1.327	0.05	1.960	Accepted
State University	2.87	0.83	120					

From the result presented in table 4, the calculated t-value at 238 degree of freedom and 0.05 level of significance is 1.327. Since the calculated t-value is less than the critical table value of 1.960, the null hypothesis is accepted.

5. Discussion

Analysis and finding in table 1 above indicated that to a high extent there is adherence to the NUC benchmark on entrepreneurship education in federal and state universities in Anambra state. However, data in table 1 shows that all the items had mean scores above 2.50 except item 4 and 8, which entails that specified objectives were not attained and unavailable resources were not improvised. Though the institutions are adhering to the use of the NUC curriculum benchmark on entrepreneurship education, method of teaching adopted may have been the reason why the specified objectives are not being attained. Therefore, it is pertinent that the universities should adopt appropriate teaching method in teaching of entrepreneurship education and effort should likewise be made to improvise unavailable resources.

Table 2 reveals that entrepreneurial practical skills to a high extent are taught in federal and state universities in Anambra State. In using entrepreneurship education to address the high rate of graduate unemployment in the nation, focus on practical skills cannot be over emphasized. Skills acquisition is the key in the fight for the elimination of hunger and poverty, reduction of joblessness and crime in the society through effective engagement of youths (Olanipekun & Adeyera, 2018). Graduates with relevant skills with or without being employed will be fully engaged in the society contributing to the development of the nation.

Similarly, Table 3 shows that none of the responses had a mean score below 2.50 except item 17. This depicts that to a high extent facilities are made available for teaching of entrepreneurship education in federal and state universities in Anambra State. This finding is contrary to that of Nwite (2016) who observed that entrepreneurial learning environment and support tools were not available in higher institutions in Nigeria and that adequate teachers to provide the needed appropriate skills and right attitude were not available and where they were available, they were in shortfall. The reason for this disparity in the findings of this study and that of Nwite could be as result of development of entrepreneurship centres in the universities, which has helped to create enabling environment for entrepreneurial learning in universities specifically in federal and state universities in Anambra state.

Nevertheless, the mean response on item 17 indicates that entrepreneurship workshops are not sizeable to accommodate all students offering entrepreneurship course, thus this calls for improve funding of entrepreneurship education to enable expansion of the entrepreneurship centres to equate the number of students being admitted in the universities.

The hypothesis tested in table 4 shows that there is no significant difference between the mean rating of students of federal and state university students on the extent of utilization of entrepreneurship education curriculum in tertiary institutions in Anambra State. This implies that the extent of utilization of entrepreneurship education curriculum is the same across the federal and state universities in Anambra state. This might be as a result of the fact that both the federal and state university managements

are well informed of the entrepreneurship education and the benefits it offers towards addressing the high rate of graduate unemployment.

6. Conclusion

This study has emphasized that graduate unemployment is one of the most critical problems facing Nigeria and this lead to the introduction of entrepreneurship education in higher institutions. The initiative of the National University Commission (NUC) in drafting a benchmark curriculum for entrepreneurship education in universities has made significant contribution in encouraging a positive orientation and imparting skills in university undergraduates.

The findings of the study indicate that to a high extent NUC benchmark is used in teaching of entrepreneurship education, entrepreneurial practical skills are taught and facilities are made available for teaching of entrepreneurship education in federal and state universities in Anambra State respectively. From all indication, continuous utilization of this entrepreneurship curriculum with innovation will change the mindset of tertiary education graduates from job seekers to job creators.

6.1 Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

- 1) University management should endeavour to adopt appropriate teaching methods in teaching of entrepreneurship education to enable the achievement of the specified objectives in equipping the undergraduate with relevant skills for self-sustainability on graduation.
- 2) Entrepreneurship education should continue to be practical oriented so as to sustain students' interest.
- 3) More allocation of resources should be designated to entrepreneurship education to enable the equipment of university entrepreneurship centres.

References

- Adejimola, A. S. and Olufunmilayo, T. (2009). Spinning off an entrepreneurship culture among Nigerian University student; prospect and challenges. *African journal of Business Management*, 1 (3) 80-88
- Aliu, S. (2014). Basic entrepreneurship education training for teachers in post-basic institutions. *Staola Centre for Entrepreneurship Development*, 1 (1) 1-6.
- Edokpolor, J. E. and Somorin, K. (2017). Entrepreneurship education programme and its influence in developing entrepreneurship key competencies among undergraduate students. *Problems of Education in the 21st Century*, 75(2) 144-153. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/316693152>

- Ekoja, I. I. & Odu, A. O. (2016). Developing and implementing entrepreneurship curriculum in Nigerian library and information science programmes. *International Journal of Library and Information Science*, 8(6) 15-30.
- Hadiza, H. & Garba, S. (2015). Assessing the richness of entrepreneurship education curriculum content: Empirical Evidence. *IOSR Journal of Research & Method in Education*, 5(6) 107-114.
- Ikebuaku, K. & Dinbabo, M. (2018). Beyond entrepreneurship education: Business incubation and entrepreneurial capabilities. *Journal of Entrepreneurship in Emerging Economies*, 10(1)154-174. Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108>
- National Bureau Statistics (2018). Unemployment and underemployed watch in Nigeria- (Quarter 4). Abuja: National Bureau of Statistic, Publication.
- National Universities Commission (2007). Benchmark minimum academic standards education documents for undergraduate programmes in Nigerian universities. Abuja: NUC.
- Nwekeaku, C. (2013). Entrepreneurship education and challenges to Nigerian Universities. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 4(3) 51-56.
- Nwite, O. (2016) Rational for youth preparation and entrepreneurship education in the face of global economic crisis in Nigeria. *Annals of Modern Education* 1(1); 224-232.
- Wordu, & Adeeyo, E. S. (2019). Entrepreneurship programmes in higher institutions in Nigeria: Extent of implementation in Rivers State. *World Journal of Entrepreneurial Development Studies*, 3(1)11-23.
- Obi, M. N. & Okekeokosisi, J. C. (2018). Extent of implementation of national entrepreneurship curriculum in tertiary institutions as perceived by educators. *American Journal of Education and Learning*, 3 (2) 108-115.
- Olanipekun, L. O. & Adeyera, B. E. (2018). The impact of entrepreneurship skill acquisition on fresh graduate self-employability status: A study of Olabisi Onabanjo University fresh graduate students. Afribary.com: Retrieved September 15th, 2019, from <https://afribary.com/works/the-impact-of-entrepreneurship-skill-acquisition-on-fresh-graduate-self-employability-status-a-study-of-olabisi-onabanjo-university-fresh-graduate-students-1209>
- Yahaya, U. (2006). Why we set up entrepreneurship studies in University. Abuja: *Monograph* (2).

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